

Diagrammatic reasoning in Euclides da Cunha's *Os Sertões (Rebellion in the Backlands)*

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To those surprised to see the engineer's prose before the poet's verses, I say that not all is strikingly decisive in this profession of numbers and diagrams.
Euclides da Cunha (1907)

A diagram is mainly an icon, and a icon of intelligible relation.
C.S.Peirce (CP 4.513).

A diagram has got to be either auditory or visual,
the parts being separated in the one case in time,
in the other in space”
C.S.Peirce (CP 3.418).

Abstract: The *Poética de Os Sertões (Poetics of Rebellion in the Backlands, 2010)*, featuring essays by Haroldo and Augusto de Campos, uncovers complex “poetic layers” within the prose of Euclides da Cunha. For the poet and translator Augusto de Campos, there are metrical verses in *Os Sertões (Rebellion in the Backlands)*, “subterranean poems” within the prose — which I interpret here as “hidden diagrams.” The distinctive “tone” of Euclides’ text, characterized by its “rhythmic density, plasticity, and sound,” results from an operation that can be described as typically diagrammatic (*sensu* Charles S. Peirce). My analysis suggests that Euclides employs a form of “iconic calculation,” where the interplay of interrelated prosodic, phonetic, and syntactic structures generates a distinctive tension between the temporal act of reading and the spatial organization of the text. I aim to offer a framework with implications that can be generalized to various instances of diagrammatic reasoning in literature. In my argument, the “physicality of the Euclidean sign,” or the “pregnant areas of poetry” in his prose, has a diagrammatic nature.

Key-words: diagrams, iconic calculation, poetry and prose, *Os Sertões*, Euclides da Cunha.

1. Introduction

Os Sertões (Rebellion in the Backlands), by Euclides da Cunha, one of the greatest classics of early 20th-century Latin American literature, is an unclassifiable work. Just a few days after its publication, José Veríssimo, one of the most important literary critics of the time, suggested in *Correio da Manhã* that *Os Sertões* was a “work of literature, history, and science, initiating a standard of interpretation that would endure for a long time” (Ventura, 2002). Its resistance to orthodox forms of classification ranges from scientific journalism to the regionalist novel, novel-poem-epic (Coutinho, 1952), historical critical essay (Oliveira, 1983), sociological essay (Freitas, 1904 [1902]), geographical essay (Azevedo, 1950), pamphlet (Sena, 1963), naturalist epic (Chaves, 1966), tragedy (Proença, 1971), work of fiction (Coutinho, 1995), verbal art (Haroldo de Campos, 1997, p. 55), work of art (Zilly, 2002), hybrid form (Gutiérrez, 2015), versified prose-poetry (Queiroz, 2014; Augusto de Campos, 1997), among others.

For the poet and translator Augusto de Campos (2010, p. 14), there are metrical verses in *Os Sertões* — “I found in *Os Sertões* more than 500 significant decasyllables, predominantly sapphics (accented on the 4th and 8th syllables) and heroics (accented on the 6th), along with a little over two hundred dodecasyllables, among which are many perfect Alexandrines.” *Poetics of Os Sertões* (1997, revised in 2010) reveals a complex weave of subliminal nature in the prose of Euclides da Cunha. Campos resumes and expands the pioneering “prospection project” of *Os Sertões* by Guilherme de Almeida, originally published in 1946, and reveals new structures — decasyllabic and dodecasyllabic — “barely hidden” under Euclides’ prose. For Augusto de Campos (2008, pp. 297–298),

Euclides da Cunha wrote poetry and had a strong knowledge of meter, although he did not produce anything significant as a poet. On noticing the well-defined rhythmic patterns in his prose, I thought it would be interesting and useful to highlight and accentuate them. While researching this theme, I stumbled upon the articles of Guilherme de Almeida, who, although not prominent during his involvement with our Modernism, was an exceptional verse maker. These studies deprived me of the priority of the critical discovery but, at the same time, validated my findings, showing me that I was not alone in my reflections. I paid homage to my predecessor in the book I wrote on the subject. The difference lies in the fact that I went deeper, presenting an objective demonstration by extracting alleged “poems” from Euclidian prose.

Whether such structures result from a controlled exploration by Euclides, or whether they are “outcomes of pure intuition or conscious craftsmanship” (Campos, 2010, p. 27), it does not matter in the domain of empirical findings about the phenomenon. The most relevant fact is that there exist, in Euclidian prose — apparently more frequently at the end of paragraphs — structures of versification with varied rhythmic patterns, which can be treated as typically diagrammatic (*sensu* Charles S. Peirce). In Portuguese, the system of versification is accentual-syllabic — one counts the number of syllables in each verse and observes the alternation between strong, accented syllables (Spina, 2003). This alternation establishes a set of patterns which, combined with hemistich markers or positional repetitions of the accented syllable, creates internal segments that define the rules of versification, or metrification.

A “verse-spectral reading” (Campos, 2010, p. 14) reveals varied structures, although Augusto de Campos and Guilherme de Almeida prefer to focus on the most well-known patterns. Augusto notes this variety — “the rhythmic movement of his sentences goes far beyond conventional counts, with the predetermined accentual-syllabic crystallization as relevant components only in key points of his propositions” (Campos, 2010, p. 16) — and informs us that he has identified more than five hundred decasyllables in the book, among sapphic and other meters, and more than two hundred dodecasyllables (Campos, 2010, p. 14), revealing a writer who “knows how to use versification resources to build areas pregnant with poetry in significant sections of his prose” (Campos, 2010, p. 180).

If my perspective is correct, it can provide a yet unexplored approach to the phenomenon and can, at least in principle, be generalized for several case analyses. In my argumentation, these

“poetic aspects of Euclidian language” (Campos, 2010, p. 13) suggest a method whose application depends on a type of diagrammatic iconic calculation.

2. Icons and diagrams

We know that, according to Charles S. Peirce, icons are signs (S) that represent their object (O) through similarity, without considering any spatio-temporal connection they might have with existing processes or entities (CP 2.299; Queiroz, 2023; Atã & Queiroz, 2014). If S is a sign of O by virtue of a certain quality that S and O share, then S is an icon of O. Furthermore, if S is an icon of O, it also communicates to an interpreter (I) a quality of O. However, the ideas of analogy and similarity, central to the thesis of the aesthetic-iconic sign, can also be developed in new directions. When an operational criterion is adopted (Hookway, 2002; Atã & Queiroz, 2013), the icon is defined as anything whose manipulation can reveal more information about its object. All formalizations, such as algebra, syntax, diagrams and graphs, can thus be recognized as icons.

The key of iconicity is not perceived resemblance between the sign and what it signifies but rather the possibility of making new discoveries about the object of a sign through observing features of the sign itself. Thus a mathematical model of a physical system is an iconic representation because its use provides new information about the physical system. This is the distinctive feature and value of iconic representation: a sign resembles its object if, and only if, study of the sign can yield new information about the object. (Hookway, 2002, p. 102)

An icon, therefore, can be characterized as a sign that reveals information through a procedure followed by observation. This definition, according to Stjernfelt (2007), represents a detrialization of the notion of the icon as a sign of similarity. This property serves as an operational elaboration of the concept of similarity. The icon is not only the only type of sign that directly presents qualities belonging to its object; it is also the only sign through which it is possible, by direct observation, to discover something about its object.

When an icon is considered to consist of interrelated parts, and since these relations are subject to experimental manipulation governed by laws, we are working with diagrams. A diagram, therefore, is an icon of relations (NEM 4:316; Johansen, 1993, p. 99). In the typology of icons, the diagram forms the second sub-category among the three types of hypoicons — images, diagrams, and metaphors (Farias & Queiroz, 2017, 2006). The object of the diagram is always a relation, and its interrelated parts represent the relations that constitute the object being represented. However, there is another element in the definition that should be noted, and it is fundamental to the characterization of the diagram: a diagram is an icon of the object in terms of the relations between its parts, but what makes it suitable for experimentation is the fact that it is constructed through intelligible relations — “A diagram is mainly an icon, and an icon of intelligible relations” (CP 4.513).

We observe this particular property in the phenomenon that interests us, as verbal signs are not predominantly iconic. Arnold (2011, p. 17) highlights that Peirce himself suggested systems of

verbal and acoustic signs can produce iconic representations (CP 3.418). Additionally, Peirce emphasizes that the “physical properties” of verbal discourse can be manipulated to reveal important information about the object. As he argues (1985, p. 48):

sound may also represent geometrically, as it often does in the icon involved in indexes, through its properties of volume, pitch, and duration. Volume and pitch are both naturally fit to diagram the quantity or intensity of any variable. [...] The duration of sounds and the spaces of silence between them are ideally suited to representing relations involving time and velocity.

Regarding the phenomena of verbal and acoustic diagrams, several authors have noted that Peirce himself suggested that sound-sign systems are capable of producing diagrammatic representations of reality.

Such a diagram has got to be either auditory or visual, the parts being separated in the one case in time, in the other in space. [...] Such a method of forming a diagram is called algebra. All speech is but such an algebra, the repeated signs being the words, which have relations by virtue of the meanings associated with them. (CP 3.418)

3. Euclides da Cunha “[...] in this profession of numbers and diagrams”

It is easy to conclude that the structures revealed by Almeida and Campos, based on the alternation of accentual-syllabic patterns, result from the manipulation of relational icons. A pattern is usually defined as a consistent arrangement of items. When “strict metrification” is disregarded and “more rhythmic freedom” is allowed (Campos, 2010, p. 29), the morphological variety of patterns found creates surprising tension zones, “areas pregnant with poetry in significant sections of his prose” (Campos, 2010, p. 18), especially at the beginning and end of paragraphs, as stressed by Almeida and Campos (2010, p. 32). The diagrammatic nature of these operations, which correspond to a type of constraint applied to the sentence, results in various paramorphisms. The Euclidian “method” probably consists of a “reverse engineering” of the sentence (see the Conclusion below), previously decomposed into a complex of part-part/part-whole relations based on heterometric patterns of versification.

The regular reiteration of these patterns would produce a monotonous effect. The irregular distribution of regular structures, more or less explicit beneath the superficial layer of phonic nature, with alliterations and puns densely accumulated at various points, confers on Euclidian prose the “peculiar tonus which is its most impressive mark” (Campos, 2010, p. 30). Campos stresses the use of “typically poetic resources,” such as “alliterations,” “hissings,” “internal echoes,” and “puns,” which are not directly connected to the construction of the “verses” (Campos, 2010, pp. 26–28). Guilherme de Almeida also emphasized the use of images — “the great book of Euclides is profuse with ‘imagerie’” (2010 [1946], p. 60) — as well as the exploration of other forms of “audible orchestration.” However, the investigation of such forms is beyond the scope of my approach because they involve non-diagrammatic, non-relational icons: the imagetic hypoicons (see Farias & Queiroz, 2006), which, as Guilherme de Almeida suggests, have clearly figurative tendencies, such as the virtuosity of the “mimetic sound”

(Almeida, 2010 [1946], p. 62). The relational structures we have examined are directly linked to rhythm and meter and can be isolated from their phonic elements for analytical purposes. In the work following the first publication of Augusto de Campos (*Os Sertões dos Campos*, 1997), Haroldo de Campos states, when discussing the difficulties of translating Euclides' work into German: "The main problem to be faced in the translation of these key sections is the question of rhythm, of the prosodic balance of the Euclidian sentence, woven from the phonic microstructure of the text" (Campos, 1997, p. 57). Any attempt to translate Euclidian prose must objectively address this iconic-diagrammatic phenomenon.

Let us examine some of the verses — decasyllables and dodecasyllables — selected by Augusto de Campos:

- “É uma paragem impressionadora.” (p. 25)¹
 “É uma mutação de apoteose.” (p. 56)²
 “Entra-se, de surpresa, no deserto.” (p. 86)³
 “É a escarpa abrupta e viva dos planaltos.” (p. 87)⁴
 “É o homem permanentemente fatigado.” (p. 130)⁵
 “Vimo-lo neste `steeple-chase' bárbaro.” (p. 131)⁶
 “Decorre-lhes a vida variada e farta.” (p. 137)⁷
 “E assim passam numa agitação estéril.” (p. 139)⁸
 “É o prelúdio da sua desgraça.” (p. 149)⁹
 “É mais um inimigo a suplantar.” (p. 152)¹⁰
 “Esta ilusão é empolgante ao longe.” (p. 276)¹¹
 “Ali estava -defronte- o sertão...” (p. 278)¹²
 “Correra nos sertões um toque de chamada...” (p. 333)¹³
 “Foi uma diversão gloriosa e rápida.” (p. 350)¹⁴
 “Não o combate; cansa-o. Não o vence; esgota-o.” (p. 466)¹⁵
 “Irrompiam, troteando, no terreiro...” (p. 509)¹⁶
 “E o dia derivou tranquilamente.” (p. 591)¹⁷

¹ “It is an impressive bit of country.” Almost all the translations of Euclides presented here are free translations, done by myself. Some I was able to locate in Putnam's translation (1944) and are marked accordingly.

² “It is a mutation of apotheosis.”

³ “One enters, unexpectedly, into the desert.”

⁴ “It is the abrupt and vivid escarpment of the plateaus.”

⁵ “It is the man perpetually fatigued.”

⁶ “We saw him in this barbaric 'steeple-chase.'”

⁷ “Their life unfolds varied and abundant.”

⁸ “And so they pass in sterile agitation.”

⁹ “It is the prelude to their misfortune.”

¹⁰ “It is one more enemy to overcome.”

¹¹ “This illusion is captivating from afar.”

¹² “There it was—before us—the backlands...”

¹³ “A call had echoed through the backlands...”

¹⁴ “It was a glorious and swift diversion.”

¹⁵ “It does not fight him; it wears him out. It does not defeat him; it exhausts him.”

¹⁶ “They burst into the courtyard, trotting...”

¹⁷ “And the day drifted peacefully.”

“Era a suprema petulância do bandido!” (p. 597)¹⁸

“Um primor de estatuária modelado em lama.” (p. 601)¹⁹

“Terminara afinal a luta cruelíssima...” (p. 628)²⁰

Still, according to Augusto, “let us note these distich-paragraphs, the first composed of two decasyllables” —

“A terra é o exílio insuportável, o morto um bem-aventurado sempre.” (p. 158),²¹

The second, by an Alexandrine and a heroic decasyllable, dominated by the accent on the sixth syllable —

“Toda a expedição caiu, de ponta a ponta, debaixo das trincheiras do Cambaio.” (p. 291)²²

4. Metric template in verse and prose

The operation of graphic division in Euclidian prose, also attempted by Guilherme de Almeida, emphasizes the diagrammatic (visual and acoustic) aspects, as claimed by Augusto: “In general, I only separate lines to highlight the most expressive rhythms” (2010, p. 29). This operation enables the visualization of relations hidden beneath the surface, as in the example:

Soldado

I

O sol poente desatava, longa,
a sua sombra pelo chão
e
protegido por ela –
braços longamente abertos,
face volvidas para os céus –
– um soldado descansava.

Descansava ...

havia três meses.

II

– braços logamente abertos,
rosto voltado para os céus,
para os sóis ardentes,
para os luars claros,

¹⁸ "It was the ultimate audacity of the bandit!"

¹⁹ "A masterpiece of statuary sculpted in mud."

²⁰ "At last, the cruelest struggle had ended..."

²¹ "The land is unbearable exile; the dead are always the blessed ones." (trans. Putnam, 1944, p. 158)

²² "The entire expedition fell, from end to end, under the trenches of Cambaio."

para as estrelas fulgurantes ...²³

In another passage, Augusto de Campos states — “I have reconstructed ‘O Prisioneiro’ more freely, but even here, there was no change to the text. Disregarding the punctuation, only the graphic layout is new.” (Figure 1)

Figure 1. O Prisioneiro.²⁴

²³ “arms thrown wide and face turned heavenward-beneath the ardent suns, the bright moons, and the gleaming stars.” (trans. Putnam, 1944, p. 24)

²⁴ “One of them, in a half-fainting condition, supported under the armpits by a soldier on either side, had a scar on his naked bosom which stood out sharply, the mark left by the saber which had laid him low.” (trans. Putnam, 1944, p.437)

This passage by Euclides da Cunha —

De repente estruge ao lado um estrídulo tropel de cascos sobre pedras, um estrépido de galhos estalando, um estalar de chifres embatendo; tufa nos ares, em novelos, uma nuvem de pó; rompe, a súbitas, na clareira, embolada, uma ponta de gado; e, logo após, sobre o cavalo que estaca esbarrado, o vaqueiro, teso nos estribos... (Cunha, 1984, p. 56)²⁵

is “recreated,” as follows, by Guilherme de Almeida (2010 [1946], p. 62) —

A Vaquejada

... De repente estruge ao lado
um estrídulo tropel de cascos sobre pedras,
um entrépido de galhos estalando,
um estalar de chifres embatendo;
tufa nos ares, em novelos,
uma nuvem de pó;
rompe, a súbitas, na clareira,
embolada, uma ponta de gado;
e, logo após,
sobre o cavalo que estaca esbarrado,
o vaqueiro teso nos estribos...

And by Augusto de Campos (2010, p. 36) —

De repente
estruge ao lado um
estrídulo tropel de cascos sobre pedras,
um
estrépido de galhos estralando,
um estalar de chifres embatendo,
tufa nos ares, em novelos,
uma nuvem de pó;
rompe, a súbitas, na clareira,
embolada,
uma ponta de gado e logo após,
sobre o cavalo que estaca esbarrado,
o vaqueiro
teso nos estribos...

²⁵ “Then suddenly, from one side, comes the noisy clatter of horses’ hoofs over rocks, the sound of cracking branches, the clashing of interlocked horns; small clouds of dust go up in the air, and there bursts into the clearing a part of the herd, their horns padded with leather balls, followed by the cowboy standing tense in his stirrups ...” (trans. Putnam, 1944, p. 98)

This is not a new strategy. According to Bradford (1993, p. 40), John Livingstone (1919) “‘found’ poetry in the prose of George Meredith and arranged it visually to refocus the reader’s ‘conventional expectations, modes of attention, and interpretative strategies.’” Visual form, however, is a secondary product within the more “phonocentric” hierarchy that prioritizes rhyme and meter as the main components. Bradford (1993, p. 40) summarizes this opinion by highlighting that visual form functions as a secondary system of punctuation — “spacing operates as a secondary system of punctuation which must defer to the dominance.”

The verse line can also be defined as a diagram from which it is possible to discern a pattern that precedes what is observed as a rhythmic “local event” (Bradford, 1993, p. 5). The visual form of a poem indicates how it should behave acoustically (Bradford, 1993, p. 228). Its graphic form directly influences its interpretation. This dual pattern arises from the interplay between graphic form and acoustic performance. If the performance depends on the graphic structure, this association (more or less ambiguous and tensioned) must inevitably influence interpretation.

The design — or, more superficially, the layout — of the poem or the verse within the poem privileges regular reiteration, transforming it into a constituent of space (clearly, seeing and hearing a poem are very distinct activities). When a particular layout or template is constructed, the format and syntactic arrangement can be reimagined, altering both reading and interpretation. It is well known, for example, that graphically and spatially arranged words become more “free” from grammatical constraints. The diagrammatic structures reaffirmed in Euclidian prose create a surprising tension between the design of the sentence, whose elements are presented successively, and the metric structure “obtained” in the temporal act of reading, where “verses” emerge as “subterranean poems.” For Jakobson, the effect produced by the verse is closely tied to the experience of time —

I am convinced that verse is maximally effective at making us experience verbal time, and this holds just as true for oral, folkloric verse as it does for written, literary verse. Verse, whether rigorously metrical or free simultaneously carries within it both linguistic varieties of time: the time of the announcement and the announced time. Verse pertains to our immediate experience of speech activity, both motor and auditory. At the same time, we experience the structure of the verse in close connection with the semantics of the poetic text – regardless of whether there is harmony or conflict between the structure of the verse and the semantic of the text – and in this way the verse becomes an integral part of the developing plot. It is difficult even to imagine a sensation of the flow of time that would be more simple and at the same time more complex, more concrete and yet more abstract. (Jakobson, 1983, p. 74-75)

Parallelisms operate on multiple layers or levels (graphic, prosodic, phonetic, etc.). If the visual format of a poem is an icon of its acoustic performance (see Bradford, 1993, p. 28), it reveals a prosodic and metric structure that precedes the specific event and context of its instantiation. In a poem written in verse, the regular juxtaposition of temporal determinants functions as an interface with the record of acoustic performance. The graphic form not only serves as a record of performance but also actively functions as a constraint that shapes it. In the case of Euclides, a

tension or disjunction emerges between the temporal movement of reiterated structures and their visually observed arrangements.

5. Final comments

The “most impressive mark” of Euclidian prose is an operation only apparently executed with symbolic components. The notion of “iconic calculation” allows us to understand how the control exerted over certain patterns — arrangements of items distributed consistently beneath the prose — is based on diagrammatic operations. Pignatari (2004, p. 119), in an approach aligned with this one, states that the “peculiar anagrammatic, hypogrammatic, and anaphonic” method of Edgar Poe requires a “process of semiotic transcoding to ‘reveal’, “the iconic nature of the poetic sign, contradicting the predominantly symbolic nature of the verbal sign, so that the jakobsonian poetic function is no more than the iconization of the symbolic sign, that reveals in fact the tangible aspect of signs.”

If an icon is examined as consisting of interrelated parts, and if these relations are subject to experimental changes controlled by rules or laws, we are operating with a diagram. In the case of the diagram, what is communicated is the structure of the sign itself — its internal arrangement. The diagram is a scheme of its object in terms of the relations between its parts, but it is only suitable for experimentation because it is built from intelligible relations. Through the operational criterion of the icon, we can appreciate the function of discovery achieved through the manipulation of diagrams. While icons focus on aspects associated with the physicality of the sign, diagrams emphasize its relational aspects — the part-part and part-whole nature of which it is composed. In my argument, the “physicality of the sign” in the passages “pregnant with poetry” in Euclidian prose has an iconic-diagrammatic nature.

There are many iconic entities and processes operating in the text of Euclides — phonic, prosodic, and syntactic. What Augusto de Campos and Guilherme de Almeida have revealed are the diagrammatic icons that constitute fundamental parts of *Os Sertões*. The objects of the revealed structures are classes of versification patterns. When well-known and historically established, these diagrammatic structures acquire a normative character. In Peirce's most detailed classification, we observe an icon whose general object produces a rhematic interpretant, or a legisign whose object — a symbol — produces a rhematic effect.

This approach can have several implications for topics such as the relationship between literature and mathematics, as well as creativity and diagrammatic thinking. For Peirce, diagrammatic thinking encompasses any form of “valid necessary reasoning” (CP 1.54, 5.162). He claims to have developed the concept of diagrammatic thinking to describe the specific nature of “mathematical thinking.” In the Carnegie Application, he emphasizes the significance of his discovery as follows —

The first things I found out were that all mathematical reasoning is diagrammatic and that all necessary reasoning is mathematical reasoning, no matter how simple it may be. By diagrammatic reasoning, I mean reasoning which constructs a diagram according to a precept expressed in general terms, performs experiments upon this diagram, notes their

results, assures itself that similar experiments performed upon any diagram constructed according to the same precept would have the same results, and expresses this in general terms. This was a discovery of no little importance, showing, as it does, that all knowledge without exception comes from observation. (NEM 4: 47-48)

My approach can provide a new set of ideas and topics for discussion about the various forms of relationships between diagrammatic thinking, poetry, and literature. If a characteristic mode of “iconic thinking” predominates in the manipulation of several semiotic processes, it is because, according to Peirce, “diagrammatic reasoning is the only really fertile reasoning” (CP 4.571). Whether such an operation can be treated as a “method” is a question to be addressed in another work. This idea finds a powerful analogy in Edgar Poe, about whom Pignatari states (2004, p. 117), based on Jakobson:

This master of writing backwards,” this “deliberate experimenter in regressive and anticipatory creation” — in the curious definition of Jakobson — is notable not only for his fair knowledge of mathematics and the mechanical and technical sciences of his time, or for his ability to assemble machines, as understood by Araripe Jr. (though it could also refer to the war machines he learned to operate at West Point), but mainly for his “discovery” of the code of written language, his extensive journalistic experience, and his close contact with typographic techniques — especially the processes of composition and printing.

Acknowledgment: Thanks to Augusto de Campos for the conversation and for the various explanations regarding the recreation of the “poem” Rodeio. Queiroz also thanks CNPq (National Council for Scientific and Technological Development) for the support through the research scholarship (PQ2 308355/2023-7) and the regular research project (Emerging Groups; 404770/2023-1).

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